

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Supplemental Material S1. List of Publications of the Database.

Ahmed, M., A. Riaz, N. Ahmad, M. Naveed ul Haque, H. ul Rahman, M. Yaseen, T. Ashraf, M. Abdullah, A. Hassan, and A. Husnain. 2025. Effect of dry period length and prepartum fat supplementation on energy balance, uterine health, and production of dairy cows. *J Dairy Sci* 108:8831–8843. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2024-26061>.

Andrade, F.L. de, J.P.P. Rodrigues, E. Detmann, S. de C. Valadares Filho, M.M.D. Castro, A.S. Trece, T.E. Silva, V. Fischer, K. Weiss, and M.I. Marcondes. 2016. Nutritional and productive performance of dairy cows fed corn silage or sugarcane silage with or without additives. *Trop Anim Health Prod* 48:747–753. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11250-016-1020-y>.

Bach, A., M. Escartín, C. Culley, A. Macdonald, J.N. Joergensen, O.C.M. Queiroz, and B.I. Cappellozza. 2025. Effects of supplementing a Bacillus-based direct-fed microbial on ex vivo fermentation traits and on performance of lactating Holstein dairy cows. *J Dairy Sci*. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2025-27134>.

Bakhshizadeh, S., F.M. Aghjehgheshlagh, A. Taghizadeh, J. Seifdavati, and B. Navidshad. 2019. Effect of zinc sources on milk yield, milk composition and plasma concentration of metabolites in dairy cows. *S Afr J Anim Sci* 49:884–891. <https://doi.org/10.4314/SAJAS.V49I5.11>.

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Barros, T., M.A. Quaassdorff, M.J. Aguerre, J.J.O. Colmenero, S.J. Bertics, P.M. Crump, and M.A. Wattiaux. 2017. Effects of dietary crude protein concentration on late-lactation dairy cow performance and indicators of nitrogen utilization. *J Dairy Sci* 100:5434–5448. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2016-11917>.

Benninghoff, J., G. Hamann, H. Steingäß, F.J. Romberg, K. Landfried, and K.H. Südekum. 2017. Effect of replacing maize grain and soybean meal with a xylose-treated wheat grain on feed intake and performance of dairy cows. *Arch Anim Nutr* 71:246–255. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1745039X.2017.1312863>.

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